

EVORoads

Evolutionary Solutions for Realising
a Holistic Safe System Approach
for All Road Users

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY, PLAN & KIT

Project deliverable D5.1

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

DELIVERABLE ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION	1
LIST OF CONTRIBUTORS	2
QUALITY CONTROL.....	2
VERSION HISTORY	2
LEGAL DISCLAIMER	2
LIST OF FIGURES	4
LIST OF TABLES	4
PROJECT EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
DELIVERABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1 INTRODUCTION.....	8
1.1 OVERALL APPROACH.....	8
1.2 MAPPING EVORoads OUTPUTS	8
1.3 DELIVERABLE OVERVIEW AND REPORT STRUCTURE	9
2 EVORoads COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY	10
2.1 WP5 OBJECTIVES.....	10
2.2 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION DEFINITIONS.....	10
2.3 COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES	11
2.4 DISSEMINATION OBJECTIVES	12
2.5 TARGET AUDIENCES AND KEY MESSAGES	12
2.5.1 <i>Target audience types</i>	12
2.5.2 <i>Key message</i>	14
2.6 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ROLE AND RESPONSIBILITIES	14
2.6.1 <i>Notification and approval of communication and dissemination activities</i>	15
2.6.2 <i>Reporting on communication and dissemination activities</i>	15
2.7 STRATEGY TIMELINE	15
3 COMMUNICATION PLAN	17
3.1 CORPORATE IDENTITY	17
3.1.1 <i>Master logo</i>	17
3.1.2 <i>Colour combination</i>	17
3.1.3 <i>Spacing</i>	17
3.1.4 <i>Incorrect use</i>	18
3.1.5 <i>Typography</i>	18
3.1.6 <i>Templates</i>	19
3.2 EU FUNDING REFERENCE	20
3.3 DIGITAL TOOLS	21
3.3.1 <i>EvoRoads project website</i>	21
3.3.2 <i>News articles</i>	22
3.3.3 <i>Social media channels</i>	22
3.3.4 <i>Newsletter</i>	23
3.3.5 <i>Standard presentation</i>	23

3.3.6	Press releases	23
3.3.7	Videos	23
3.4	PRINTED MATERIALS	23
3.4.1	Flyer/postcard	23
3.4.2	Roll-up.....	23
3.5	COMMUNICATION KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs)	23
4	DISSEMINATION PLAN	25
4.1	DISSEMINATION CHANNELS.....	25
4.1.1	Scientific publications.....	25
4.1.2	Non-scientific publications.....	25
4.1.3	Dissemination events.....	25
4.1.4	European Commission Dissemination and Exploitation Tools	27
4.2	LIAISON AND ENGAGEMENT WITH OTHER EU INITIATIVES.....	27
4.3	DISSEMINATION KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs).....	27
5	CONCLUSION	29
ANNEX	30
CORPORATE IDENTITY - LOGO COLOUR VARIATION.....	30	

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1.	Overview on objective, focus and target audience of communication and dissemination.....	11
Figure 2.	EvoRoads logo	17
Figure 3.	Colour palette	17
Figure 4.	Spacing around logo.....	18
Figure 5.	Incorrect logo uses	18
Figure 6.	EvoRoads typefaces.....	19
Figure 7.	PPT Template	19
Figure 8.	Deliverable template.....	20
Figure 9.	Meeting minutes template	20
Figure 10.	EU-funding statement options	21
Figure 11.	Website landing page.....	21
Figure 12.	Dissemination and Exploitation tools	27

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1:	Adherence to EvoRoads GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions	9
Table 2.	Target audiences	14

Table 3. Communication KPIs	24
Table 4. Preliminary list of targeted events	27
Table 5. Dissemination KPIs	28

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	MEANING
CCAM	Cooperative, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EC	European Commission
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
STEEP	Social-Technological-Economic-Environmental-Political
WP	Work Package

PROJECT EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

EvoRoads is committed to advancing the European Union's Vision Zero initiative by implementing a comprehensive framework that integrates innovative models, tools, and services for data-driven safety assessments. The project focuses on enhancing the safety of cyber-physical infrastructures and providing proactive risk warnings in complex environments.

The project defines safety criteria and quantification methods for key performance indicators (KPIs) within the "Safe System" framework. It involves the development of a connectivity platform that digitalizes transport infrastructure assets and ensures the seamless integration of safety assessment services. By leveraging advanced artificial intelligence, EvoRoads analyses infrastructure monitoring data at various geospatial levels, enabling proactive risk warnings and supporting road operators in managing maintenance more effectively, which enhances both safety and operational efficiency.

EvoRoads' methodologies and technologies will be validated in four Living Labs situated in Spain, Italy, Latvia, and Romania. These labs will address diverse road user scenarios across urban and rural environments to ensure broad applicability and effectiveness.

Social Media link:

For further information please visit evoroads-project.eu

DELIVERABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

EvoRoads is committed to advancing the European Union's Vision Zero initiative by implementing a comprehensive framework that integrates innovative models, tools, and services for data-driven safety assessments. The project involves the development of a connectivity platform that digitalizes transport infrastructure assets and ensures the seamless integration of safety assessment services. EvoRoads enables dynamic monitoring of cyber-physical infrastructures and proactive risk warnings, and supports road operators in managing maintenance more effectively, which enhances both safety and operational efficiency.

The current document D5.1 “Dissemination/Communication Strategy, Plan & Kit” presents the EvoRoads dissemination and communication strategy and plans, detailing the activities to be conducted throughout the project’s course to achieve maximum visibility and enhance its impact within the research community. The strategy is designed to support stakeholder engagement, facilitate the exploitation of project results, and ensure a broad and enduring impact.

The report presents the graphic elements and templates associated with the project visual identity, along with guidelines for their use. It also specifies procedures and timelines for approval and reporting of communication and dissemination activities, as well as roles and responsibilities in relation, namely the expected contributions from consortium members regarding publications, events, as well as the website and social media channels (LinkedIn and YouTube).

The document outlines the target audiences, such as public and road authorities, road operators, service providers, hardware providers, OEMs, researchers, policymakers, and users the key messages and communication & dissemination channels and tools, i.e. website, social media, newsletters, promotional materials (e.g., flyers, posters, videos), scientific publications, project events, external conferences, to be utilised, as well as the Key Performance Indicators defined to measure the effectiveness of the strategy.

Additionally, liaison activities with related projects, e.g., [SOTERIA](#), [SELFY](#), [PoDIUM](#), [ShippingLab Autonomy](#), [RONDA](#), [FRODDO](#), [CulturalRoad](#), [iDriving](#) are planned to facilitate knowledge transfer and build synergies.

In the first phase of the project, communication activities will focus on providing general information. As the project progresses and results mature, dissemination activities to engage stakeholders with targeted information on the knowledge generated within the project, to gather feedback and validate the project’s results, will become increasingly important. In the last phase of the project, the communication & dissemination strategy will support the exploitation strategies defined at the beginning of the project for the identified Exploitable Results (ER). Serving as a central resource for all planned dissemination and communication activities, this strategy lays the foundation for knowledge sharing and innovation. By combining public engagement, academic outreach, and a robust media and digital presence, the EvoRoads D&C Strategy enhances the project's visibility and supports the integration of its findings into practical applications and policies across Europe.

The document is considered a living report, and will be updated by project mid-term based on monitoring and updates of Communication and Dissemination Key Performance Indicators, and to align with the project’s technical outcomes and any new dissemination and communication opportunities.

1 INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 5.1, "Dissemination, Communication Strategy, Plan and Kit," outlines the dissemination and communication strategy and plan designed to ensure maximum visibility for the project and its outcomes. The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive guide for promoting the EvoRoads mission. It describes the available communication and dissemination tools and channels, specifies communication requirements, and outlines the targeted values to enhance the external visibility of the project. This deliverable serves as an internal guideline and is a crucial point of reference for all project partners, and it will be updated throughout the project's duration.

The dissemination level of D5.1 is public and is intended for:

- Firstly, the EvoRoads project partners. They need to be informed about the planned Dissemination and Communication (D&C) activities, how to communicate and disseminate the project themselves, as well as the roles and responsibilities, and procedures to be considered in relation (e.g., use of Corporate Identity, reference to EU funding).
- Secondly, the European Commission (EC) services. The D&C Strategy informs the EC about the planned D&C activities as well as the expected KPIs within the project.
- Finally, the project's targeted audiences who will benefit from the communication and dissemination of EvoRoads' results and findings can be interested in the set of activities planned to engage with and to communicate/disseminate these results to them.

The D&C Strategy will be updated as necessary to incorporate any required changes to the plan following the latest project developments. Updates on the progress of the planned D&C activities will occur at the project mid-term (M18).

1.1 OVERALL APPROACH

The D&C Strategy sets the basis for the dissemination and communication activities to be implemented throughout the EvoRoads project. As such, it aims to maximise the impact of the foreseen D&C tasks with respect to the project's objectives and informs about the partners' involvement. The D&C strategy fosters a joint understanding of the terms "communication" and "dissemination" themselves, their objectives and target groups in line with the European Commission's definitions.

D&C activities both serve as a transversal support to each Work Package (WP) and to the partners of the project. The communication activities are there to inform about the project itself, its activities and progress, and its results, while the dissemination activities describe and make results available for use and further uptake.

ERTICO as leader of Task 5.1 is responsible for the general development of this deliverable and is responsible for the continuous implementation and coordination of its described activities. ERTICO is also responsible for the development of the project corporate identity and in setting up the main elements of the D&C activities.

All activities related to communication and dissemination highlighted in this document impact the other tasks of Work Package (WP) 5. They contribute significantly to achieving Objective 5 (O5) of the project: "Accelerate the adoption of EvoRoads' innovations through continuous impact creation activities that ensure the exploitation and standardisation of the proposed solutions and provide policy recommendations documenting the lessons learnt." These activities serve as verification means to support this objective.

1.2 MAPPING EVOROADS OUTPUTS

The purpose of this section is to map EvoRoads Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

EvoRoads GA component title	EvoRoads GA component outline	Respective document chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLES			
D5.1 Dissemination/Communication Strategy, Plan & Kit	Overall strategy and plan for the project communication and dissemination. The deliverable defines messages, channels and tools for outreach, as well as synergies with other related initiatives and external events; a live document, kept updated on a regular basis, and at the project mid-term	Chapter 1 Chapter 2	Chapter 1 introduces the deliverable, the overall approach and the structure of the document Chapter 2 describes the communication and dissemination strategy of EvoRoads
TASKS			
Task 5.1: Dissemination and communication activities	Task 5.1 focuses on developing and implementing the communication and dissemination strategy for EvoRoads, starting with the identification of key elements as outlined in Section 2.2	Chapter 1 Chapter 2 Chapter 4	Sections 1.1 and 1.2 Section 2.1 Section 4.2

Table 1: Adherence to EvoRoads GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

1.3 DELIVERABLE OVERVIEW AND REPORT STRUCTURE

The remainder of the document is organised as follows:

- Section 2 outlines the communication and dissemination strategy for the EvoRoads project, detailing its objectives, target audience, communication and dissemination roles and procedures.
- Section 3 depicts the communication plan, including the corporate identity (logo, usages, EU funding, etc.), digital communications tools (website, social media accounts) and printed materials. It also describes the Communications Key Performance Indicators related to the implemented tools.
- Section 4 presents the EvoRoads dissemination plan, in particular dissemination steps, channels, and the associated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for measuring dissemination effectiveness.
- Section 5 offers concluding remarks.

2 EVORoadS COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

2.1 WP5 OBJECTIVES

The objectives of Work Package 5 (WP5) encompass defining and implementing a comprehensive Communication and Engagement Plan (Task 5.1). This involves developing marketing materials and promotional tools, including the project website, social media platforms, flyers, booklets, posters, videos, and e-newsletters. These efforts target a broad range of stakeholders, such as public and road authorities, road operators, service providers, hardware providers, OEMs, researchers, policymakers, and users.

Additionally, WP5 aims to facilitate knowledge transfer and build synergies by liaising with related projects, including [SOTERIA](#), [SELFY](#), [PoDIUM](#), [ShippingLab Autonomy](#), [RONDA](#), [FRODDO](#), [CulturalRoad](#), and [iDriving](#). This is crucial for fostering collaborative efforts.

WP5 also focuses on providing deployment guidelines for practitioners and policymakers (Task 5.2). This includes promoting the integration and real-time monitoring of safety KPIs and criteria within the digital ecosystem, ensuring comprehensive stakeholder connectivity.

Finally, to maximise the project's impact beyond its duration, WP5 involves developing an exploitation strategy, technology roll-out plan, standardisation framework, and business plan (Tasks 5.3 and 5.4). This includes analysing relevant standards for infrastructure monitoring and maintenance and creating a Multiplier Group to enhance interaction with existing programmes at national, European, and global levels.

2.2 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION DEFINITIONS

Ensuring a clear understanding of the terms 'communication' and 'dissemination' is imperative for the successful execution of EvoRoads. The European Commission has distinguished between Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities' characteristics in an online document¹ and the consortium's interpretation is founded upon them (see Figure 1).

¹ European Commission, European Research Executive Agency, *Communication, dissemination & exploitation what is the difference and why they all matter*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2848/289075>

Figure 1. Overview on objective, focus and target audience of communication and dissemination

2.3 COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES

Communication involves spreading general information about the project and its results, such as current or planned activities, focusing on the project's overall relevance to society. This should happen early, as soon as information is available, to ensure timely updates to interested parties.

The strategic approach for EvoRoads Communication will be based on the Lasswell model of five levels of communication: who (Source), what (Message), through which medium (Channel), to whom (Audience), and to what effect. This strategy will be developed in accordance with the European Commission's recommendations on Communication and Dissemination.

The Communication Strategy will ensure a clear agreement among partners on the following key elements:

- The specific objectives for each target audience, as mentioned in paragraph 2.5.
- The channels and means to be used, tailored to the specific needs and nature of each audience.
- The activities to be performed at each development phase and the materials to be released, depending on the project's progress.
- Key measures for evaluating the effectiveness of communication and dissemination efforts.
- The procedures to be followed and the roles of all consortium partners in relation.

Communication measures are considered successful if a significant number of people become aware of the challenges being addressed by EvoRoads and the developed solutions. Success is measured by KPIs detailed in Chapter 3.

Information will be shared through digital and printed formats, including websites, social media, newsletters, articles, press releases, and flyers, as well as through oral presentations at events and videos. Further details are provided in section 3.3 and 3.4.

2.4 DISSEMINATION OBJECTIVES

Dissemination involves spreading information about the technical and scientific results of the project for others to use during the project’s lifetime and beyond. This information is disseminated in a publishable format, adhering to open access requirements and ensuring sensitive technical details are appropriately shared.

To facilitate further development, replication, exploitation, and market uptake of the EvoRoads results, the project’s dissemination activities aim to:

- Ensure maximum visibility of the project among the target audiences through appropriate key messages
- Timely disseminate the scientific and technological knowledge generated within the project both within and beyond the Consortium.
- Establish connections with other projects for the transfer of knowledge and innovation.
- Engage target audiences to obtain feedback and validate the project’s results.
- Attract potential users and clients, stimulating relevant market segments to support the project’s exploitation strategy
- Encourage the development of derived outcomes in new initiatives

Dissemination activities, as well as liaisons with other projects and Road Safety Initiatives, will be closely monitored and evaluated against a set of predefined KPIs (in Table 3) throughout the project lifecycle, with results presented in each reporting period.

2.5 TARGET AUDIENCES AND KEY MESSAGES

2.5.1 TARGET AUDIENCE TYPES

The table 2 below identifies the potential targeted audiences of EvoRoads along with their specific interest in the project.

Dissemination Audiences	Main Benefits
<p>Public Authorities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cities and municipalities/ local authorities (including relevant departments, e.g. traffic management, road transport • National ministries of Transportation and Infrastructure, national Road and Traffic Authorities • Regional Road and Traffic Authorities • Road Operators • Road Infrastructure managers • Traffic management units • Police 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of EvoRoads infrastructure safety KPIs, automated and remote infrastructure sensing for asset management, warning and advising services for safer travelling; • Ensuring safety of services provided • Ensuring compliance with safety standards/ regulations • Training on project’s outcomes; • Participation in the project’s events, namely to validate new safety KPIs
<p>Service Providers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connected vehicle data providers • Infrastructure/ road maintenance operators/crews/providers 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public transport operators/providers Taxi Micromobility service providers (e.g. ridesharing) 	
<p>Industry</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Road Equipment and hardware providers Vehicles developers (e.g. OEMs, powered-two wheelers and micro mobility) Smart city solutions and CCAM technology providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participation in ecosystem building events; Exploitation of project's open-source results; Inspiration for new ideas and applications
<p>Road/traffic/safety Associations & Technology Clusters</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inclusion of project's results to collaborative research activities (roadmap, white papers, etc.); Dissemination of project's results to their members; Bilateral participation in events for knowledge exchange, validation of new safety KPIs
<p>Horizon Europe projects</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common research topics for synergies and collaborations Enhancing innovation through results combination Co-organisation of joint dissemination activities for results promotion Participation in events for knowledge exchange, validation of results
<p>Researchers and Academia</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further advance the project's research; Extension / reuse of the project's innovative technologies to other application domains; Inspiration for future research initiatives based on the project's concept and results; Participation in the project's events.
<p>Policy Makers & Standardisation Organisations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EC institutions MS Ministries and Governments Standardisation Organisations, Regulatory Agencies, (CEN, ISO, ETSI, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of EvoRoads infrastructure safety KPIs in EU and national policies Definition of future research and innovation directions based on project's acquired knowledge; Evaluation of the project's Social-Technological-Economic-Environmental-Political (STEEP) aspects; Inputs for standardisation activities
<p>General Public</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Civil society representatives, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and Advocacy Groups Community and Citizen Groups/associations (school, parents, neighbourhoods) Road users seeking improved safety in their every-day travels, including but not limited to powered two- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilise the project's results in their daily lives Understand the benefits offered by the project's results in their daily lives (e.g. safer routes for children traveling to and from school) Take part in the Living Lab activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide feedback on local transport and safety issues, ensuring community needs are addressed. Utilise the project's results in road safety advocacy and education campaigns, in sustainable mobility advocacy

wheelers, cyclists, e-bikers, pedestrians, drivers)	promoting cycling and walking as safe and viable modes of transport
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Table 2. Target audiences

2.5.2 KEY MESSAGE

The key message of the EvoRoads project underpins all dissemination and communication (D&C) activities. This core message effectively emphasises the EvoRoads aims to accelerate the achievement of the European Union's Vision Zero goal through a holistic framework of innovative models, tools, and services that enable data-driven evolution of safety assessment frameworks:

“EvoRoads is committed to advancing the EU’s Vision Zero goal by providing innovative models and tools for data-driven safety assessments. EvoRoads defines clear safety criteria and develops a connectivity platform that digitalises transport assets for integrated safety and maintenance management. The project enhances road safety as well as road operators’ efficiency through dynamic monitoring of cyber-physical infrastructures and proactive risk warnings.”

The core message serves as a foundation for creating more targeted and audience-specific messages, which will be defined in the course of the project, with the help of other WPs, and be used by the EvoRoads partners for communication and dissemination. When necessary, these key messages will be translated into local languages and tailored to address specific target groups, ensuring effective outreach to various audiences.

2.6 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ROLE AND RESPONSIBILITIES

Different roles are required to ensure adequate implementation of the D&C activities. The following section describes the roles and responsibilities of consortium partners in relation as well as the communication flow between ERTICO as leader of Task 5.1 and other EvoRoads partners.

The team:

- ERTICO: Serves as the main point of contact for all interested press and media in English and leads WP5. It oversees primary project communications and supplies consortium members with the necessary materials and texts. ERTICO manages the main communication materials and channels, including the project website, newsletter, press releases, and social media channels like YouTube and LinkedIn. Additionally, ERTICO handles external communication with related EU institutions, initiatives, projects, stakeholders, and other multipliers.
- All partners strongly support ERTICO in the D&C activities and contribute to their content development, as required, as well as their dissemination through their own channels, networks and dissemination activities.
- WP Leads: Provide regular updates to ERTICO about their WP activities and progress for further promotion.
- Living Labs: Are responsible for promoting the project through their local and regional channels. This includes distributing the project newsletter, translating and sharing press releases, and disseminating project news via their organization's websites and social media channels. They keep ERTICO informed about their local activities and results.

2.6.1 NOTIFICATION AND APPROVAL OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

EvoRoads consortium members wishing to participate in an event or undertake dissemination activities to (re)present the project must obtain prior approval from the Dissemination Manager (and EC Project Officer, through the Project Coordinator, for activities outside Europe). They must inform the Dissemination Manager, who will in turn notify all partners in the case of a foreseen publication. In the latter case, notification must be given to the other consortium members at least thirty (30) calendar days before the planned publication. Any objections to the planned publication must be made in writing to the Coordinator and the proposing Party or Parties within twenty (20) calendar days after receiving the notice. If no objections are raised within this timeframe, the publication is permitted.

All consortium members engaging in communication and dissemination activities (such as scientific papers, presentations at external events, press releases, articles, videos, or any printed materials like posters) must (1) always acknowledge the EC funding in these (see chapter 3.2), and (2) record these in the internal EvoRoads Dissemination Activities register. This record must include all necessary details and each column in the table must be thoroughly completed (type of activity, partners involved, description, date, location, website URL and target audience). This register will serve as the basis for reporting all Communication and Dissemination activities to the European Commission as required by the Grant Agreement.

These procedures aim to:

- Ensure high-quality publications and presentations.
- Avoid overlap and potential disclosure of sensitive or confidential information.
- Monitor and record all dissemination activities efficiently.

2.6.2 REPORTING ON COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

As a project funded by the European Commission (EC), EvoRoads must periodically report its communication and dissemination activities to the EC, detailing materials, events, outreach efforts, and audiences. To facilitate this, it is essential for all partners to meticulously document their communication and dissemination activities. A Dissemination register will be set up and managed by ERTICO and stored on the EvoRoads (internal) online collaboration tool.

The Dissemination register must be updated as soon as the dissemination activity is confirmed, and the entry updated within five days of completing any communication or dissemination activity, including links to presented materials (final papers, presentations, posters, etc.), and, where possible, a copy of said materials should be stored in a dedicated folder on the (internal) online collaboration tool.

2.7 STRATEGY TIMELINE

The timing, duration, and frequency of communication and dissemination activities vary throughout the project. In the first phase, communication activities focused on providing general information will take priority. As the project progresses and results mature, dissemination activities with targeted information will become increasingly important. A preliminary roadmap of the dissemination strategy steps is presented below:

- Preparation phase (M1-M12): In this phase, EvoRoads establishes a central theme, which includes designing a logo to make the project's brand easily recognisable and memorable for the audience, along with developing key messages. The project also plans activities to engage stakeholders and raise awareness about EvoRoads, while identifying current or potential stakeholders.
- Execution phase (M13-M24): EvoRoads actively engages its targeted audience in the project's activities to co-create solutions and disseminate the scientific and innovation knowledge generated within the project. The aim is to ensure both mid- and long-term impact by ensuring maximum visibility of the project among target audiences through appropriate key messages and by timely diffusing the scientific and technological knowledge generated within and beyond the project's consortium and its networks. In this phase, new liaisons with other EU-funded

projects for knowledge and innovation transfer will occur, and EvoRoads will also engage the targeted audiences to gather feedback and validate the project's results.

- Exploitation phase (M25-M36): In the last phase of the project, the communication & dissemination strategy will support the exploitation strategies defined at the beginning of the project for the identified Exploitable Results (ER).

3 COMMUNICATION PLAN

This Section describes the communication plan of the EvoRoads project, in terms of objectives, corporate identity, communication channels and tools, as well as communication Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

3.1 CORPORATE IDENTITY

The EvoRoads project logo should reflect its essence while being concise and modern. As a result, the EvoRoads logo combines elements of road safety, innovation, and technology, creating a cohesive and uncluttered image.

3.1.1 MASTER LOGO

The EvoRoads logo presented in Figure 2 must appear fully intact. It must not be altered or distorted in any way. Guidelines for the correct use of the logo must be respected in terms of the minimum size and colour options. Whenever the logo is used, it should be surrounded by clear space to ensure its visibility and impact. No graphic elements of any kind should enter this zone.

Figure 2. EvoRoads logo

3.1.2 COLOUR COMBINATION

The primary decision in selecting the colour palette was the use of a gradient, which reflects the project's dynamism, its connection to technology, and development. The main shades are blue and violet, with an orange shade chosen as an accent. Additionally, a supplementary purple shade can be used if needed. The colour palettes are differentiated for digital and printing endeavours.

Figure 3. Colour palette

3.1.3 SPACING

The security field defines the minimum allowable distance from the logo to other elements of the layout. It is not permissible to place graphic or text elements inside the security field.

Figure 4. Spacing around logo

3.1.4 INCORRECT USE

When using the logo, it is important to follow specific guidelines to preserve its integrity. Firstly, you should not alter the proportions of the logo elements. At the minimum size, the master logo should always be used in full. All elements must appear in relation to each other as designed. No variation of proportion or position should occur. Additionally, avoid transforming, adding, or removing any individual elements of the logo. Distorting the logo—such as tilting it or changing its perspective—is also prohibited. Outlining the logo is not allowed, and the colours used should be strictly those specified in the brand book; do not recolour the logo with any other hues. The spacing between the logo elements must remain consistent and unchanged. Mirroring the logo or its elements, whether individually or as a whole, is not permitted. Similarly, the application of effects or textures to the logo should be avoided. Lastly, ensure that the logo is placed on a contrasting background to maintain visibility and clarity.

Figure 5. Incorrect logo uses

3.1.5 TYPOGRAPHY

The logo font is Prompt Medium Italic. Additionally, two different fonts have been selected to address the communication and dissemination needs of the project. Prompt light/regular will be used for external communication materials, such as brochures, posters, leaflets, roll-up banners and website. Arial typeface will be used for working documents such as deliverables, slides, etc., for internal and official documents.

LOGO FONT

Prompt Medium Italic

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNPOQRSTUVWXYZ
1234567890 .,-+!N°&@«»

BRAND FONT

Prompt Light

Prompt Medium

FONT FOR THE INTERNAL DOCUMENTS
 (DELIVERABLES, SLIDES, ETC.)

Arial

Prompt Regular

Prompt SemiBold

Arial

Figure 6. EvoRoads typefaces

3.1.6 TEMPLATES

3.1.6.1 POWERPOINT

A Microsoft PowerPoint (PPT) presentation template for the EvoRoads project has been developed (Figure 7). The template consists of a slide deck with the EvoRoads logo and includes an opening slide, slides for bullets and tables and a closing slide.

Figure 7. PPT Template

3.1.6.2 OTHER TEMPLATES (DELIVERABLES, MEETING'S MINUTE)

Standard Microsoft Word templates, in keeping with EvoRoads brand guidelines, have been developed for EvoRoads deliverables (Figure 8) and meeting minutes (Fig. 9).

Figure 8. Deliverable template

Figure 9. Meeting minutes template

3.2 EU FUNDING REFERENCE

As the project is funded by the European Union (EU), communication and publication materials should clearly acknowledge receipt of EU funding through the display of the EU emblem and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate). The EU funding statement (Figure 10) must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

**Funded by
the European Union**

**Funded by
the European Union**

Figure 10. EU-funding statement options

For correct use of the EU emblem and funding statement, please use the following link:
https://commission.europa.eu/documents_en.

3.3 DIGITAL TOOLS

3.3.1 EVORoads PROJECT WEBSITE

The EvoRoads project website address is www.evoroads-project.eu

Before the launch of the fully developed website, the following landing page is available at that URL.

Figure 11. Website landing page

The website will be structured to display information about the project in a transparent and accessible manner. The preliminary structure defined comprises the following (sub-)menus:

- Homepage
- About
 - Objectives
 - Stakeholder categories
 - Consortium
- Key Innovations
- Living labs

- Spain
- Italy
- Romania
- Latvia
- Library
 - Deliverables
 - Publications
 - Media
 - Brochure and flyer
 - Newsletters
 - Project presentations
 - Video repository
- News & Events
- Contact

3.3.2 NEWS ARTICLES

The overall production of news articles will be overseen by ERTICO. These articles will contain information about the project and updates from partners, including events, ongoing activities, and milestones. These non-scientific articles, published on the project website, will inform a broad audience and rely on active contributions from partners who will help write the articles. All news articles will be promoted via social media channels and the EvoRoads newsletter.

The key performance indicator is to publish at least 10 news articles on the EvoRoads website. More articles will be published based on the availability of news updates from the Consortium members, particularly from the living labs.

3.3.3 SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS

The project's online presence is crucial for achieving our communication and dissemination performance targets. To foster online engagement, EvoRoads will be active on LinkedIn and YouTube. These social media platforms will be utilised to enhance the project's outreach in a more general and immediate manner, playing a vital role in increasing the project's visibility and engaging with a broader audience.

All partners are requested to:

- Follow the EvoRoads account on LinkedIn.
- Reshare the social media original posts.
- Contribute articles and/or news items whenever possible.

Two equally valid approaches are suggested:

1. Have the project's profiles share the news item.
2. Personally create and post the content, then have the project's profiles re-share it.

Consortium partners are encouraged to engage on the project social media channels by initiating discussions, re-sharing relevant posts, events and news items related to the project's activities. Additionally, when posting EvoRoads-related content on corporate or personal social media accounts, partners should ensure to:

- Tag the project and any other relevant accounts properly.
- Include #EvoRoads hashtag

3.3.3.1 LINKEDIN

A project-specific LinkedIn company page called EvoRoads Project has been created (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/evoroads-project/about/?viewAsMember=true>). All major project updates and

announcements will be shared with the followers of this page. The page has been launched on 21 May 2024 during the project kick-off event held in Brussels.

3.3.3.2 YOUTUBE

EvoRoads project will benefit from the [ERTICO Corporate YouTube Account](#) already collecting video materials from other R&I projects in related playlists. The page counts 372 subscribers. A dedicated playlist will be created for EvoRoads.

3.3.4 NEWSLETTER

A biannual newsletter will be sent to EvoRoads subscribers and partners that are interested in staying informed on the project’s proceedings and the related latest news. A banner will be implemented on the project’s website homepage and contact page in order to allow interested partners and stakeholders to subscribe to the newsletter.

3.3.5 STANDARD PRESENTATION

A standard project presentation will be developed for use by all consortium partners in their dissemination activities. The standard project presentation will be accessible, together with the different elements of the visual identity, including the logo use guidelines, and the document templates, via the (internal) online collaboration tool.

3.3.6 PRESS RELEASES

Four press releases will be issued to mark milestones at the EvoRoads project’s Living Labs. These will be co-created with the local partners, in both English and local language, and subsequently disseminated through appropriate channels to reach the wider network.

3.3.7 VIDEOS

ERTICO will support the production of specific videos to feature the project's Living Labs, showcasing the work conducted at each location.

3.4 PRINTED MATERIALS

3.4.1 FLYER/POSTCARD

A flagship leaflet will be developed early in the project. The document will present the project concepts and will be distributed at EvoRoads events and external conferences, meetings, etc. The leaflet will also be produced in a digital version that will be downloadable from the project website in PDF version and updated as necessary during the project’s lifetime.

3.4.2 ROLL-UP

A roll-up poster will be developed to present the project, its objectives, website, social media and contact addresses, and it will be made available to all consortium partners. It will be used to promote the project at various events and workshops. Further posters may be produced, depending on the need for updates or, during the lifetime of the project, to present specific results, demonstrations/Living Labs or other aspects of the project.

3.5 COMMUNICATION KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs)

In order to maximise the impact of the communication activities and to guarantee that the EvoRoads project is promoted adequately throughout its duration, some Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were set. They are summarised in the following table.

Tools and channels	Target Value
Website	1000 unique website visitors

	<p>3000 page views</p> <p>30 links to the project's website</p> <p>10 news</p>
LinkedIn	<p>500 followers</p> <p>100 (original) and 500 (reshare, external mentions/tags) posts</p> <p>500 impressions/month</p> <p>1000 interactions</p>
Materials	<p>4 project's factsheets / brochures/ banners (incl. best practices & results booklet)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 800 downloaded /distributed booklets <p>6 Newsletters</p> <p>4 videos</p> <p>8 blog/article posts in "EU mechanisms"</p> <p>4 press releases related to pilot demonstrations</p>

Table 3. Communication KPIs

4 DISSEMINATION PLAN

The dissemination plan outlines the activities that will be supported and coordinated with communication efforts as part of Work Package 5 (WP5). The plan details our approach to delivering evidence-based results and information about the EvoRoads project to targeted audiences, ensuring their engagement and enhancing the deployment and transferability of the project's outcomes.

The dissemination plan:

- Defines dissemination channels, tools, timelines, and frequencies to avoid overlap or the potential disclosure of confidential information.
- Identifies key events, publications, and activities to achieve a high dissemination impact on the targeted audience, ensuring high-quality publications and presentations.
- Establishes engagement activities with related projects.
- Presents key performance indicators (KPIs) to record and monitor progress, ensuring the objectives of the dissemination activities are achieved in a timely manner.

4.1 DISSEMINATION CHANNELS

In addition to the communication channels described in Section 3 (printed and digital tools/materials), dissemination activities will be carried out through various additional channels, including publications, events organised by the EvoRoads project, and external conferences.

4.1.1 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

EvoRoads academic partners will actively disseminate their research and technical outcomes through scientific publications and conference proceedings in national and international journals identified by the consortium. Open access must be guaranteed for all scientific publications. The related procedure for prior notice before submission is described in Chapter 2.6.1.

All scientific publications will be published in the website “Library” with appropriate links.

Here below a preliminary list of targeted journals and conferences for the project's scientific publications:

- *Transactions of Knowledge and Data Engineering*
- *Journal of Intelligent Information Systems*
- IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing Technology and Science (CloudCom)

4.1.2 NON-SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

In addition to scientific publications, several, more general publications will be developed and published on printed or online industrial and technical journals, targeting various stakeholder groups, thus going beyond the academic community. All publications will be made available in the website “Library”.

4.1.3 DISSEMINATION EVENTS

Dissemination of the project's activities and achievements will also take place at various conferences and events—both online and in person—to raise awareness about road safety and engage relevant stakeholders and interested parties. This will primarily involve presentations in specialised sessions or through exhibition stands to promote, discuss, exchange, and disseminate the project results.

All partners are required to participate in external local, regional, national, and international events to present EvoRoads and stimulate interest from stakeholders not yet involved in the project. At relevant conferences, events, and meetings,

the project will be showcased through technical papers and presentations. Additionally, special-interest sessions and demos will be organised to present project advancements to a broad audience and gather valuable feedback. The following sections provide a detailed overview of the various types of events.

4.1.3.1 PROJECT-ORGANISED EVENTS

The EvoRoads project will feature a comprehensive programme of events designed to engage multiple stakeholders and disseminate its findings. Over the course of the project, the project will organise 12 multi-stakeholder events to foster collaboration and exchange among diverse groups, including six workshops, aligned with demonstration events at pilot sites, to provide hands-on experience and showcase practical applications or held in conjunction with external events to reach a broader audience. Moreover, four training webinars will be offered in the local languages of the pilot sites, ensuring accessibility and effective knowledge transfer. These efforts aim to train over 500 participants, equipping them with the skills and knowledge necessary to implement project outcomes.

A dedicated policy and acceleration event will be organised to discuss and promote the project's policy implications and accelerate its adoption. The project will culminate in a final event, anticipated to attract over 100 participants, where the results and achievements will be presented and celebrated.

In addition, partners will convene 20 internal and/or corporate events to share insights about the project with other departments not involved in the project or their business network.

4.1.3.2 EXTERNAL EVENTS

EvoRoads will be actively promoted through presentations at external conferences and events, related to transport, infrastructure, road safety, or specialized networks, fora and platforms (e.g. ACEA, CCAM Partnership, CEDR, ETSC) events, to enhance awareness of project's activities dependent on stakeholder engagement and support. Table 4 provides a preliminary list of such conferences and events where EvoRoads partners might showcase the project.

Event
Urban Mobility Days
ITS European Congress
ITS World Congress
IRF Global Roads for Tomorrow
European Infrastructure Conference
International Conference on Automation, Computing and Renewable Systems (ICACRS)
TRB
R&I Days
RTR Conference
ITF events
CIVINET events
European Mobility Week
EUCAD 2025

Table 4. Preliminary list of targeted events

4.1.4 EUROPEAN COMMISSION DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION TOOLS

Beneficiaries of Horizon Europe funding can benefit from free-of-charge services to support the dissemination and exploitations of project’s activities. A more detailed overview is given in the figure below and it is available on the official website of the European Commission².

Figure 12. Dissemination and Exploitation tools

4.2 LIAISON AND ENGAGEMENT WITH OTHER EU INITIATIVES

In the context of Task 5.1 and related activities, ERTICO will lead efforts to maximise the value of existing connections and foster new relationships with key projects and initiatives. This includes engaging with the [SOTERIA project](#), the [SELFY project](#), the [PoDIUM project](#), the [ShippingLab Autonomy project](#), the [RONDA project](#), the [FRODDO project](#), the [CulturalRoad project](#), and the [iDriving project](#), among others. The primary goal of this task is to enhance collaboration, facilitate knowledge exchange, encourage the cross-pollination of ideas, and amplify the impact of the project's actions. This objective will be achieved namely through joint dissemination activities designed to involve various stakeholders and partners effectively.

4.3 DISSEMINATION KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs)

² “Communication, dissemination & exploitation what is the difference and why they all matter”, publication of the European Commission for Horizon Europe projects. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/58ad3394-0a63-11ee-b12e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-287940279>

Category	Target Value
Stakeholder engagement	Network of 300 actors/contact points 8 industry sectors informed >20 cities involved
Scientific and non-scientific publications	16 conference papers 10 peer-reviewed journals papers 10 articles in industry magazines (generalist media) > 5 Master Thesis > 3 PhD Thesis
Project-organised events	12 multi-stakeholder events organised <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 workshops (↔demonstration events at pilots) • 3 physical workshops at external events • 4 training webinars in pilots' local language <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ >500 trained participants • 1 policy and acceleration event • 1 final event <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ >100 participants 20 internal partners' events
External events	30 attended events <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 15 events with project's presentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3 events with Special Session organised
Liaison with projects	5 joint activities with projects 8 projects with synergies
Standardisation	3 Working Groups 10 standardisation meetings >5 standardisation enhancements

Table 5. Dissemination KPIs

5 CONCLUSION

This deliverable presents the initial versions of the dissemination and communication plans for the EvoRoads project. The document includes:

- **Communication Plan:** key promotional materials, the appropriate communication channels and social media accounts have been set up to facilitate the achievement of the dissemination goals. The production of various promotion tools and materials, including those related to project identity, have been planned.
- **Dissemination Plan:** target groups, key messages, and associated activities have been defined and linked to tangible goals. A preliminary list of events and scientific conferences has been identified to facilitate high impact.
- **Liaison with Other Projects and Initiatives:** EvoRoads has already reached out to with other projects active in the field to foster cooperation, exchange best practices, and enhance the exploitation and outreach of project outcomes.

The implementation of this plan has already started (the project's brand has been established, social media accounts set up; the website development is ongoing and a landing page at the secured url is already available), and will continue with the development of key messages and first activities to engage targeted stakeholders and raise awareness about EvoRoads. Progress will be regularly monitored and evaluated against the KPIs, with corrective actions taken as necessary.

The EvoRoads team will utilise this document to ensure a common understanding of the procedures to be followed throughout the project's duration. This will help maintain a high-quality and consistent communication channel with the general public. The document is considered a living report, as it will be updated by project mid-term based on precise monitoring and control of EvoRoads activities, adapting to new dissemination and communication opportunities, and aligning with the project's technical outcomes and specific dissemination activities scheduled/defined (e.g., workshops, participation in large events, training activities).

ANNEX

CORPORATE IDENTITY - LOGO COLOUR VARIATION

EVORADS

EVORADS EVORADS

EVORADS EVORADS EVORADS

EVORADS EVORADS

